

Educational intervention to prevent gender violence in university nursing students: Design

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Abstract

Introduction: This study provides the PRE-VIOGEN educational program developed by seven Mexican public educational institutions with multimedia technology in distance mode, designed to prevent gender-based violence in nursing.

Objective: Design an educational intervention to prevent gender violence in nursing students.

Methodology: Descriptive design based on basic methodological recommendations from INSALUD, gender theories, feminism, Bourdieu, Ausubel, and Bandura. First, an analysis of the situation was carried out, the problem was defined, a diagnosis of the student's situation and contextualization of the conditions for educational intervention. For the systematization and integration of the content, a format was created and the themes were distributed. For implementation, the application method was systematized, piloting was carried out with a sample of convenience. For the selection, students from the 4th-10th semester with availability of a computer and internet were invited. On the Moodle platform, they were given informed consent, aspects of their participation and resolution time: distance, self-administered and asynchronous modality. For the evaluation, a satisfaction survey was applied.

Results: Sample made up of 54 students, mostly women, heterosexuals, interns, with a partner between 20 and 28 years old. The interactive PRE-VIOGEN educational program consists of 18 mixed pedagogy themes that are addressed from a gender perspective around equality, social justice, respect for diversity and exercise of human rights, distributed in 5 units. Includes guided readings, infographics, discussion forums, interactive videos, learning activities, and self-assessments. The duration is 20 hours, approximately 2 weeks. In the satisfaction survey applied, the students reported feeling very satisfied.

Conclusions: The design of the PRE-VIOGEN study program is a contribution to nursing education. It is taken in the short term, offers an emotional, social and humanities learning experience in a tele-educational-interactive mode, with the capacity to offer combined pedagogical materials: texts, sound, gamification, animation, and videos, which can be taken in the students' free time. It will contribute to evaluating the effect of educational intervention to prevent gender-based violence.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Gender-Based Violence in Schools

Gender-based violence in schools (GBVS) occurs in all cultures and countries in the world. It is a form of discrimination and violation of human rights that affects thousands of students, families, and communities. It can be defined as acts or threats of sexual, physical or psychological violence that occur in and around schools, perpetrated as a result of norms and stereotypes driven by unequal power dynamics. Experiencing violence can compromise well-being, and physical, and emotional health and harm school performance. GBVS is complex, involving structural issues, social norms, beliefs, ingrained behaviors, and everyday practices that give shape to gender and authority. The prevention of GBVS is a guiding strategy for all actions. Among the evidence-based recommendations is education, since it has an essential role in transforming the main causes of violence, especially gender-based violence (GBV). Education is an important mechanism for the social, emotional, and psychological development of young people. For the educational system, a pillar of prevention efforts is the development of educational content and delivery mechanisms. Also essential is the quality of the environment that ensures a safe and welcoming environment in which teaching, learning, work, and study take place. Likewise, it is necessary to develop clear, safe, and accessible procedures and mechanisms for reporting incidents and providing assistance to victims [1].

1.2. Trends in Nursing Education

Current education trends are framed in the 25 main educational programs in the world, which are very diverse. For example, in the US they emphasize emotions and technology. “Case1”, “Ruler”, “K12 Lab” and “Scratch” are among the most notable. In Europe, emotional education is highlighted and the most innovative countries that are at the forefront choose to educate in skills and lifelong learning. In Germany “Waldorf” is the pedagogy taught in private schools, focused on art in education. In the United Kingdom, “RSHE” (Relationships, sex, and health education) is the mandatory affective-sexual and health education program since 2020. In Latin America, innovation and language (reading) are encouraged. The Colombian program “Aprende” includes courses for teachers, infographics, and games. “A-prender la tele” is the Ecuadorian program that managed to replace in-person education during COVID-19. In Chile, “Cantando Aprendo a Hablar” is a series of videos and songs to support language development [2].

Today's society is characterized by having moved from the analog era to the digital era where new tools and a mine of information appear. Some of the education trends that will be seen more in the classrooms and will be part of how education will be transmitted are the use of artificial intelligence (refers to computer systems that seek to imitate the human cognitive function through machines, processors, and software to perform data processing and analysis tasks), immersive technologies or personalization of learning (360 content, virtual reality stand out in this sector (VR), augmented reality and mixed reality). Distance education, hybridity in formats, gamification (a learning technique that transfers the full potential of games to the educational field to improve results), and the use of chatbots (a computer program that uses artificial intelligence (AI) and computer processing). natural language (NLP) to understand customer questions and automate responses, simulating a human conversation). Alternative credentials such as on-demand learning (online workshops, courses, and degrees in asynchronous formats) are also highlighted. Therefore, distance education will grow every day. In the same way, the humanities will be in high demand when it comes to developing skills and education could be personalized according to the needs of the student body. Mental health will also play an important role in student performance. Therefore, universities will play an important role in the dissemination of science and knowledge [3].

The educational model of the New Mexican School includes critical thinking generated from analysis, reflection, dialogue, historical awareness, humanism, and founded argumentation for the improvement of the social, cultural, and political spheres. Likewise, it promotes lifelong learning, the incorporation of collaborative and innovative methods, technological advances, and scientific research, and uses creative freedom to innovate and transform reality [4]. For nursing and health sciences education, trends are found in clinical simulation and debriefing, training in clinical practice and disability, ethics and bioethics with a multidisciplinary approach, innovation in university education, educational innovation in health professional training, and lines of teaching research [5].

1.3. Distance education and multimedia technology

The world of education is moving from the traditional way of learning to new forms of distance learning through technologies or media such as computer networks, with little or no face-to-face contact between students and teachers. Likewise, multimedia technology is used, that is, materials, usually programs, that combine, partially or completely, text, sound, graphics, and video in integrated packages [6].

Study programs can be short, medium, or long term. The short-term ones offer quick and practical training, non-formal education that is offered through flexible programs, require less time commitment, are less expensive than traditional options, and do not lead to a degree but to certifications. They are ideal for developing skills, and updating knowledge and skills in the respective fields of study. They are designed and customized according to the needs and high demand in the market. Some of the most popular short-term programs abroad, located in the United States, are aimed at international business with a duration of 6 weeks in 15.5 hours, and Engineering Management with a duration of 2 weeks. In Australia internship courses in accounting, economics, marketing and sales, management, mentoring, media and communication, retail, and fashion. In Canada, 4-week business management. In Germany, 4-week automotive and mobility studies [7,8,9]. Latin America has a significant lag in this type of short-term training, they are carried out in traditional areas such as electronics, tourism, advertising, or programming, but also more innovative areas such as application design, cybersecurity, nanotechnology, or automation. industrial. In Mexico, Costa Rica, Honduras, and Panama the rate of education in this type of program is less than 5%. Colombia and Peru use this type of program between 25-30% [10]. The National Institute of Public Health in Mexico offers 20-hour courses [11].

1.4. Basic methodological recommendations for developing an educational project

A recommendation from the National Institute of Health (INSALUD) [12] is to consider the concept of education as “an intentional process by which people become more aware of their reality and the environment that surrounds them, developing knowledge, values, skills, and capacity.” that allow them to adapt, according to them, their behaviors to reality.” To develop the health education project, an introduction of the health problem that has been prioritized is required; as an analysis of the situation or previous aspects for the identification of needs. Another point is the formulation of the objectives, which responds to the needs detected, that is, the new situation that is intended to be achieved with the educational situation. Another aspect is defining the contents, which means explaining the basic concepts that we want to transmit and teach about each topic, including concepts, attitudes, values, norms, strategies, and procedures of all kinds. They must respond to the needs, problems, interests, and motivations of the group. The methodology must consider the following aspects: a) the target population to which the educational project is directed, and b) the way of attracting or recruiting the population, which can be through information posters. c) development of the intervention that includes the number of educational sessions (5 to 10 is recommended), duration of the sessions (60 to 120 min is recommended, expository techniques 20 min), and periodicity depending on the topic to be addressed. timing (dates and times). Place (it is advisable to be the same). Number of participants (20 to 25 maximum). It is advisable for educational sessions that in each session the educational technique (research, presentation, analysis, skill development, other techniques), the type of grouping (pair, small groups), the time that will be used to develop each technique, and the resources to be used (human, materials, etc.). d) The last situation to consider is the evaluation that must be established as part of the planning of a project that integrates: structure (human and material resources), process (project methodology), and results (If the short-term objectives were met, the impact of the educational intervention is evaluated).

1.5. Virtual environments

Virtual learning environments go beyond simulating a physical classroom. They are very complete tools that integrate virtual classroom and Learning Management Systems (LMS) functions. Some of the functions include storing and distributing information, such as the index of course contents, creating interactive materials and content, functioning as a social network thanks to the option of creating profiles, chats, and discussion forums, having its own graphic identity, even with augmented reality technology, turn students into actors who create the virtual space, encourage student participation and cooperative work and integrate various pedagogies, such as Flipped Learning or gamification. They are very useful to improve teaching work. Some are more specialized in content management, others in interaction with students, and others in the gamification of learning. The Moodle platform is the second most used LMS in Universities around the world and is paid. At the same time, it is a free, open-source virtual learning environment that allows you to create online courses, manage virtual classrooms, and track grades throughout the course with reports and graphs of each student's academic performance [13].

1.6. Theoretical bases

The following theoretical bases are those that support the educational program.

1.6.1. Gender theory

Gender theory is part of the historical, social, and cultural theoretical paradigm of feminism. When we talk about gender perspective, we refer to a conceptual and methodological tool to explain, understand, and transform social reality, which is a critical, scientific, analytical, explanatory, and political vision and an alternative to what happens in the order of genders, such as the characteristics that define women and men specifically, their similarities and differences. Marcela Lagarde points out that the theory is used to demonstrate situations of oppression and discomfort that women share in their struggles for equity, discrimination, and non-violence derived from sexual difference and power relations, such as subordination, the division of resources, responsibilities, attributes, capabilities, and privileges. Gender-based studies contribute to making women visible as social subjects in the context of male hegemony. In this way, gender as an analytical category transcends the idea of men and women as different realities to focus its gaze on social relations based on sexual difference that generates inequalities. The theory allows us to analyze women and men not as given, eternal, and immutable beings, but as historical, socially constructed subjects, products of the type of gender social organization prevailing in their society [14,15].

1.6.2. Feminist theory

Feminism is defined as the defense of women's human rights based on the principle of equal rights for women and men [16]. It is a radical political, social, and philosophical movement that affirms women as people with rights. It has its origins on a par with revolutionary and libertarian struggles, especially with the emancipatory ideals of the French Revolution of the 18th and 19th centuries [17]. The theory is based on different approaches and various academic disciplines, it provides the conceptual and methodological tools to study how gender, in interaction with race, class, age, ethnicity, and religion, organizes social life, and from that, it develops strategies to eliminate inequality [18]. It points out that there is a systemically articulated power structure that rests on the socio-political construction of genders. Gender is both the cause and the effect of that power structure that divides society into two asymmetrical parts, one of them marked by subordination, a deficit of resources and rights, and the other evidenced by domination, and excess of resources and rights. Structures that produce inequality, discrimination, and oppression [17,19]. The objective of feminism is to reveal the ideological mechanisms by which they are reproduced, as well as the understanding of their nature. It focuses on gender politics, power relations, and sexuality. It presents a critique of social relations, and analyzes gender inequality and the promotion and exercise of human rights. It exposes all those ideological structures and mechanisms that reproduce the exclusion of women in different areas of society [19,20]. With the feminism movement, the right to property for women has been achieved, equal pay for working-class women, women's suffrage, better education for girls of all social classes, admission to all universities and careers, non-discrimination at work, maternity rights, power to decide about one's own body, ending sexual objectification, protection services for victims of violence, among other things [16].

1.6.3. Pierre Bourdieu theory

Pierre Bourdieu's contributions reveal the objective relationships that shape and sustain social life, to understand how domination works and how inequality is generated in the complex societies of advanced capitalism. The core part is that the logic of the system is to perpetuate privilege and inequality based on the fact that society is not divided into 2 classes: bourgeois and proletarians, nor is it a society of liberals with autonomous individuals seeking to maximize their benefits. Rather, he comments on a SOCIAL SPACE in which there are different TYPES OF CAPITAL. The economic capital is constituted by factors of production: land, factories and jobs, goods, properties, and cars. Social capital is the set of social relationships: contacts, friends, relatives, habits, tastes, practices, and lifestyles. Cultural capital is what allows access to refined consumption with academic recognition. In that social space and others, global capital is distributed. For Bourdieu, SOCIAL CLASSES arise from a network of relationships that range from where one studies to what music one listens to, including sports, what one eats, and vacation places. To do this, he coins the concept of FIELDS, which are the configurations of classes or social relations where groups come together and relate. For example, the academic field brings together the university world. These relationships are based on common capital. The fields are dynamic and produce a hierarchy between those who hold power and those who aspire to have it. All fields and forms of capital are related to forms of power. The cultural field is also a terrain of power disputes, the weapons are words, traditions, and expressive forms.

Bourdieu states that the State has a legitimate monopoly on physical and symbolic violence. SYMBOLIC VIOLENCE explains the domination of class societies and that of the colonialist over the colonized, also that of man over woman, that of the school over the student, and that of the urban world over the rural world. The dominant thinks with the mental categories inherited from the dominant, for example, intelligent/ignorant, civilized/savage. The state exercises this symbolic violence in the mind, creating mental structures and forms of perception and thought.

Symbolic violence physical violence and the economy contribute to the reproduction of inequalities. This training begins from childhood and involves a process of gradual socialization that includes diverse learning: body habits, rules of courtesy, language, patriotism, and love of neighbor. Domination begins with the word, censorship mechanisms operate in language, people do not say more than what they are authorized to say, because language is an instrument of communication but also a tool of power. Bourdieu makes true cultural internationalism necessary to combat MENTAL COLONIZATION. Television is another form of manipulation and is a tool dedicated to the service of the dominant order, it has engulfed journalism and threatens to do the same with politics and culture.

All of Bourdieu's ideas must be studied as a set of relationships in what he calls the SOCIAL FIELDS, where the social structure and the individual, the objective and the subjective, intermingle.

Based on statistics and field studies, he demonstrates that educational institutions, far from strengthening democratic principles and offering egalitarian possibilities, benefit those who belong to privileged sociocultural and economic sectors, in this way they reproduce the social inequalities that they conceive as natural and irreversible [21].

The central attribute of gender violence with its typologies is that it is exercised mainly towards women, just because they are women. They are specific forms of violence, whether emotional, physical, sexual, or economic, based on structures of gender inequality that are legitimized by the set of norms and beliefs that construct women as subordinate to men. When such appreciations have been incorporated in the form of habitus, the conditions are generated to recreate that violence in the form of symbolic violence; that is, to achieve the unconscious collaboration of women in sustaining the social project of domination that subjugates them, legitimizes and reproduces the subordination of women to men. We start from the notion that the genesis of male domination according to Pierre Bourdieu [22] can be traced to the set of social practices that simultaneously legitimize and reproduce the subordination of women to men. Such practices rest on an arbitrary generic division of labor that translates into specific relations of domination, with rights, abuses, privileges, and injustices that are perpetuated thanks to the effect of symbolic violence. This becomes manifest when “the dominated apply to the relations of domination categories constructed from the point of view of the dominators, thus making them appear natural” and, for this reason, it is usually unconscious [23].

1.6.4. Ausubel's Theory of Meaningful Learning

David Ausubel's constructivist theory of meaningful learning points out that human learning goes beyond simple behavior change, it leads to a change in the meaning of experience. Human experience involves thought and affectivity, and only when they are considered together is the individual educated to enrich the meaning of her experience. He proposes that student learning depends on the previous cognitive structure (set of concepts, or ideas that an individual has in a certain field of knowledge) that is related to the new information. Ausubel describes meaningful learning as the process that is generated in the human mind when it subsumes new information in a non-arbitrary and substantive way and that requires as conditions: predisposition to learn and potentially significant material which, in turn, implies the logical significance of said material. and the presence of anchoring ideas in the cognitive structure of the learner. It is underlying the constructive integration of thinking, doing, and feeling, which constitutes the fundamental axis of human aggrandizement. He points out that the discovery-based teaching/learning model must be reconstructed by the students, before being learned and significantly incorporated into their cognitive structure [24].

1.6.5. Bandura's social cognitive learning theory

Albert Bandura's theory of social learning focuses on the concepts of reinforcement and observation and highlights the idea that a good part of human learning occurs in the social environment. By observing others, people acquire knowledge, rules, skills, strategies, beliefs, and attitudes. He also explains that people learn about the usefulness and appropriateness of various behaviors by looking at models and the consequences of their actions and acting by what they believe they should expect as a result of their actions. According to this theory, people LEARN most of their behavior through observation through MODELING. By observing others, they encode this information, which will later serve as a guide to action. This theory states that people who observe acquire symbolic representations of the activities carried out by the model. From a young age, we observe what surrounds us and with it, we learn. This is the basis of vicarious learning as we observe others and imitate them. Thus, if someone sees that a person's aggressive behavior is reinforced, then they can learn it by imitation or modeling. Bandura's work has been extraordinarily fruitful for the understanding of aggressive behavior, especially because it has allowed us to analytically distinguish the learning of a behavior and its execution; That is to say, you can learn aggressive behavior because you have seen how it was rewarded in another person, but that does not imply that you have to execute it [25].

2. Material and Methods for Design

2.1. Descriptive design study

The development of the design was based on the basic methodological recommendations to develop an educational project of the Health Institute (INSALUD) [12] and theories. First, an analysis of the situation of the students at the participating campuses was carried out through two previous investigations: in one, a multidimensional instrument was designed and validated for perception, attitudes, knowledge and gender violence to then explore and compare the prevalence, knowledge, perception, attitudes, as well as to identify spaces, types, perpetrators and consequences of gender violence in the seven Mexican public university institutions that teach nursing and a health institution: FENO, FESI, FESZ, FEUADY, FEUV, ESEO-IPN, DCBS-UAM-X and SSY. Subsequently, the problem was defined based on the results obtained.

From the first and second stages, the activities were planned. A review of the literature was carried out for the construction and theoretical foundation. Likewise, contextualization of the conditions for the educational intervention was carried out, for example, the themes, times, the number of educational units, the role that each participant will have, the first approach with the students, the review of the regulations of each university to prevent gender violence, etc. The objectives, purpose, resources, and form of writing were set out. To systematize the information, a format was created with five sections: the first contains an identification sheet where the topic to be covered is briefly described, the second implements the development of the thematic contents, the third refers to the learning activities, The fourth establishes the evaluation system and the last constitutes the references used. For the integration of the educational program, the themes for its development were distributed by headquarters, which were reviewed together for the necessary adjustments. For the implementation, the way of working was analyzed for the first approach and systematization of the application method. A pilot study was carried out with a sample of convenience, which was selected with a call inviting enrolled students and academic level from the 4th to the 10th semester to participate in the educational program, as a requirement they requested having a computer, internet, knowledge minimums for uploading and downloading files and familiarization with an educational platform. Those interested contacted the person responsible for the intervention via telephone or email. Subsequently, they were given access to the Moodle platform through a link sent to the participant's email where they were given informed consent through which their participation was validated, emphasizing that collaboration is free and voluntary. The objective of the project and aspects of their participation were made known.

The presentation of the educational program was distributed in 5 units that included directed readings, interactive videos, and learning activities continued, the duration (20 hours) taken asynchronously over a period of two weeks. They were also made aware of the associated risks, privacy and confidentiality of the data provided, and freedom to withdraw at any time they consider appropriate, without affecting their condition and institutional rights. To evaluate the program, a satisfaction survey was applied, and based on the results, pertinent modifications were made.

3. Results

3.1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the sample

The piloting was carried out with 47 university students (Table 1) with similar sociodemographic characteristics: nursing students between 20-30 years old, from the 5th and 10th semesters.

3.2. Satisfaction survey. The majority of nursing students were very satisfied and satisfied with the educational program. They provided information from their perception of the materials that seemed most user-friendly and suggestions for improving the program (Table 2).

3.2. Educational program

The program design consisted of 5 units taken in a virtual environment asynchronously with a duration of 20 hours. The themes are based on a mixed pedagogy that is addressed from a gender perspective around equality, social justice, respect for diversity, and the exercise of human rights. It includes guided readings, interactive audio videos, cases, discussion forums, and downloadable learning activities (Table 3).

Table 1 Sociodemographic data of Nursing Students

Table 1. Sociodemographic data of Nursing students												
Institution	Sample	Sex		Age	sexual orientation				with couple	Single	Academic level	
		Man	women		Hetero	Bi	Demi	Trans			10°	5°
FENO	7	3	4	22-26	5	2	-	-	4	3	7	-
SSY	13	2	11	22-25	10	2	-	1	8	5	13	-
FESI	7	2	5	21-30	7	-	-	-	3	4	7	-
FESZ	5	1	4	23-26	4	-	1	-	5	-	5	-
FEUADY	10	1	9	21-24	8	2	-	-	6	4	10	-
FEUV	3	1	2	20-21	3	-	-	-	2	1	1	2
ESEO	1	-	1	30	1	-	-	-	1	-	1	-
UAM-X	1	-	1	28	1	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
Total	47	10	37	20-30	39	6	1	1	29	18	45	2

Source: Google forms database Pilot Study of Gender Violence in Nursing Students PAPIIT IN304521 ENEO-UNAM 124. December 2022

Table 2 Satisfaction survey PRE-VIOGEN Education Program

Table 2. Satisfaction Survey PRE-VIOGEN Educational Program		
Indicators	Scales	Answers
Teaching materials	Very satisfied	63%
	Satisfied	26%
	Neutral	11%
	Not at all satisfied	0%
Application Time	Ideal	56%
	Insufficient	14%
	Overly	30%
Application difficulty	Very easy	33%
	Easy	11%
	Neutral	30%
	Difficult	23%
Satisfaction	Very satisfied	56%
	Easy	33%
	Neutral	11%
	Not at all satisfied	0%
Friendly Material	Videos	Readings
	Infographics	
	Forums	Learning activities
	Cases	Information
Recommendations for Improvement	Reduce videos	
	Remove repetitive content	
	Improve clarity in instructions	
	Reduce learning activities	

Source: Survey prepared by the author of the Educational Program, January 2023.

Table 3 PRE-VIOGEN Educational Program

Table 3. PRE-VIOGEN Educational Program		
Unit	Thematic content	Time
1	Legal, historical, political and social framework on which human and gender rights are based for a life free of violence against women.	4 hours
2	Basic concepts of gender perspective, roles, identity and gender stereotypes.	4 hours
3	Power relations, social inequalities and gender violence.	4 hours
4	The social construction of romantic relationships and violence in couples.	4 hours
5	Harassment, sexual harassment, prevention practices, care, punishment and repair of damage.	4 hours

Source: Program developed with the support of the participating headquarters of the PAPIIT Project IN304521 ENEO-UNAM 124. January 2023.

4. Conclusions

This PRE-VIOGEN educational program opens learning spaces with mixed pedagogical strategies and uses ICTs, of short duration, where students create their schedule based on a mosaic of themes. It integrates emotional and social education, critical thinking, and humanism. It offers an attractive learning experience, with the capacity to provide combined teaching materials: guided texts, learning activities, sound, gamification, animation, and videos in a tele-educational-interactive mode that can be taken in the student's free time. Its purpose is to raise awareness and positively influence the change in perspective that can be introjected by non-violent behaviors that reflect in models aimed at strengthening gender identity, self-esteem, autonomy, and empowerment concerning gender violence so that allows you to build your learning, rebuilding attitudes and values that guide performance in professional practice for the care of people, which implies recognition, attention, prevention, and reporting.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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